

line transplanting, one pellet every four hills (15 × 20 cm). Quantities of gliricidia green leaves (containing 2.7% N oven-dried basis) to supply 0, 1, 1.5, 2, and 2.5 t green manure/ha were spread uniformly over freshly puddled soil before line transplanting. Karjat-184 was transplanted (3-wk-old seedlings) 7 Jul and harvested 12 Oct.

Deep-placed USG significantly increased grain and straw yields (see table). Deep-placed USG at 38 kg N/ha plus green manure increased grain yield more than split-applied PU. □

Effect of USG and PU with limited gliricidia green manure on rainfed transplanted rice yield.^a Maharashtra, India, 1988 wet season.

Urea N (kg/ha)	Treatment		Yield (t/ha)		Tillers/hill (no.)
	Green manure t/ha	kg N/ha	Grain	Straw	
0	0	0	2.8 c	3.1 d	7.9 e
38 (PU)	0	0	3.0 c	3.2 d	9.7 de
38 (PU)	1	6.3	2.9 c	3.4 d	12.5 abc
38 (PU)	1.5	9.5	2.9 c	3.2 d	10.3 cde
38 (PU)	2	12.6	3.2 bc	3.8 cd	11.1 bcd
38 (PU)	2.5	15.8	3.5 b	4.5 bc	11.9 bcd
38 (USG)	0	0	3.8 ab	4.7 bc	13.0 ab
38 (USG)	1	6.3	3.9 a	5.1 ab	13.5 ab
38 (USG)	1.5	9.5	4.0 a	5.7 a	12.5 abc
38 (USG)	2	12.6	4.2 a	5.5 ab	14.6 a
38 (USG)	2.5	15.8	3.9 a	5.2 ab	15.1 a

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

Integrated nutrient management in irrigated rice

M. R. Patel, N. P. Chauhan, S. A. Patel, and J. G. Patel, Gujarat Agricultural University, Main Rice Research Station, Nawagam, Gujarat, India

We studied the integrated effect of organic and inorganic sources of N on growth and grain yield of rice variety GR11 during 1987 wet season. Eight fertilizer combinations were tested (see table).

The test soil was sandy loam with a pH of 7.3, EC 3.5 dS/m, 0.065% total N, 68.5 kg available P/ha, and 332.8 kg available K/ha.

P and K were applied basally; N as ammonium sulfate was applied in four equal splits; basal and at tillering, panicle initiation, and dough stage.

Azolla was inoculated at 1 t/ha 10 d after transplanting (DT). Because of an erratic rainy season, water was not impounded and azolla grew very poorly. The azolla mat was incorporated 30 DT.

Sesbania aculeata was incorporated 1 d before transplanting.

Before incorporation azolla had 2.8% N, 0.48% P, and 3.2% K; *S. aculeata* had 2.5% N, 0.64% P, and 1.0% K.

Delayed planting due to failure of the monsoon and use of brackish irrigation water from a bore well decreased yields.

Grain yield with *S. aculeata* + 40-20-20 kg NPK/ha and *S. aculeata* + 0-20-20 kg NPK/ha were significantly higher than all other treatments except 80-40-40 kg NPK/ha alone and *S. aculeata* + azolla + 0-20-20 kg NPK/ha. □

Effect on rice yield of N applied during reproductive phase

P. C. Pandey, P. S. Bisht, and P. Lal, Agronomy Department, G.B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, Nainital 263145, Uttar Pradesh, India

In the subtropical climate of north India, rice grown with recommended best N split (1/2 basal, 1/4 at tillering, 1/4 1 wk before panicle initiation) or standard split (2/3 basal, 1/3 1 wk before panicle initiation) has luxuriant vegetative growth but the canopy turns light green during ripening. We tested supplying a larger proportion of N during reproductive stages (1 wk before panicle initiation, at booting, and at heading), at 120 and 180 kg N/ha. The field experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with four replications in wet season 1988 at Pantnagar (29° N, 79° 29' E, 244 m).

Soil was silt loam with pH 7.9, 1.1% organic C, CEC 20 meq/100 g soil, 0.1% total N, 13.9 kg available P/ha (Olsen), and 202 kg available K/ha (NH₄OAc extraction).

Pant Dhan 4 (134 d duration) was sown 1 Jun and transplanted 5 Jul with basal application of 17.6 kg P, 24.2 kg K, 10 kg Zn/ha.

Effect of organic and inorganic sources of N on yield and panicles/m². Nawagam, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles/m ² (no.)	Biomass (t/ha) incorporated
Control	0.8	108	—
0-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	0.8	128	—
40-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	2.0	196	—
Azolla + 0-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	1.0	119	3.2
Azolla + 40-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	1.9	171	1.8
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i> + 0-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	3.3	307	26.4
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i> + 40-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	3.7	300	22.7
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i> + azolla + 0-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha	2.8	240	24.9
80-17.6-33.2 kg NPK/ha	3.1	258	+1.5
LSD (0.05)	1.1	75	—

Effect of split N application on grain yield, panicle numbers, and filled grains and unfilled grains of rice.^a Pantnagar, India, 1988.

N application					Grain yield (t/ha)			Panicles/m ² (no.)			Filled grains/panicle (no.)			Unfilled grains (%)		
Basal	Tillering	6-7 DBPI ^b	Boot	Heading	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean	N ₁₂₀	N ₁₈₀	Mean
1/2	1/4	1/4	–	–	6.2	6.8	6.5	184	183	184	136	132	134	11	17	14
2/3	–	1/3	–	–	6.5	6.8	6.7	182	193	188	126	125	126	20	19	20
1/5	1/5	1/5	1/5	1/5	6.9	7.9	7.4	183	197	190	147	132	140	08	12	10
1/4	1/4	1/6	1/6	1/6	6.9	7.4	7.2	191	188	190	141	134	138	10	10	10
Mean					6.6	7.2		185	190		138	131		12	15	
Treatment					LSD (0.05)			LSD (0.05)			LSD (0.05)			LSD (0.05)		
N rate					0.4			ns			ns			ns		
Time of N application					0.5			ns			ns			4		
Interaction																
N rate at same or different time of application					ns			ns			ns			ns		
Time of N application within a N rate					ns			ns			ns			ns		
CV (%) based on error b					7			7			7			28		

^ans = nonsignificant. ^bDays before panicle initiation.

Response to N application time was significant (see table). Applying N 1/5 or 1/4 as basal and 1/5 or 1/6 N

topdressed 1 wk before panicle initiation, booting, and heading increased grain yield 10%. The increase

in yield was primarily due to more filled grains per panicle. □

Effect of single superphosphate and granular superphosphate fertilizer on rice yield

M. L. Adil, J. R. Patel, and S. C. Mukharjee, Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya, Raipur 492012, Madhya Pradesh, India

We compared response of rice to single superphosphate (SSP) (16% water soluble and 2% citric soluble P₂O₅) and granular superphosphate (GSP) (14.8% water soluble and 3.6% citric soluble P₂O₅) during 1987 wet season.

Medium-duration cultivar Kranti was transplanted 20 Jul 1987 and harvested 4 Nov 1987. Soil was medium heavy (sandy loam) with pH 6.7, 0.42% organic C, CEC 32.6 mg/100 g, and 210 kg available N, 10.5 kg available P, and 325 kg available K/ha. All treatments received 60-40-20 kg NPK/ha except that the control plot received no P. N was applied in three splits: 50% basal, 25% topdressed at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation.

For both SSP and GSP, treatments were all P as basal, all P at tillering, and

Effect of P source on rice yield and yield attributing characters. Raipur, India, 1988.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Effective tillers (no.)	Panicle length (cm)
Control (no P)	2.9	3.6	3.8	14.1
GSP at transplanting	3.9	4.8	4.0	15.0
SSP at transplanting	4.8	5.9	5.6	16.2
GSP at tillering	3.7	4.6	4.0	14.3
SSP at tillering	4.3	5.2	5.0	15.8
GSP: 50% at transplanting, 50% at tillering	4.1	5.1	5.0	15.1
SSP: 50% at transplanting, 50% at tillering	5.3	6.4	5.8	17.1
LSD (0.05)	0.8	0.8	ns	

split P, 50% at transplanting and 50% at tillering.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Plot size was 144 m²; plant spacing was 20 × 20 cm.

Reduction of rice yield without any P fertilization was significant (see table). Applied as basal, SSP was much superior to GSP. Yield was significantly higher with SSP split application.

The relatively higher availability of P in water-soluble SSP might have made the difference under wetland conditions. □

Performance of *Sesbania rostrata* in acid soils

M. A. Salam, S. M. S. Hameed, P. Sivaprasad, E. Tajuddin, and Y. Thomas, Cropping Systems Research Center (CSRC), Karamana, Trivandrum 695002, India

We compared *S. rostrata*, a newly introduced green manure crop, with *S. aculeata* and *Crotalaria juncea*, green manure crops commonly grown in Kerala.